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Research Article

**IMPACT OF SMOKING ON ERYTHROCYTE
SEDIMENTATION RATE (ESR) AND LIPID PROFILE IN
ADULTS**¹Dr Aliya Maryum Salman, ²Dr Arslan Nasir, ³Dr M.Muzzamil Yasin Khan¹Lahore Medical and Dental College²Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur³Quaid-e-Azam Medical College, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of the study was to understand the changes in ESR and serum lipid profile in adult smokers and non-smokers and the risk of developing atherosclerosis.

Study design: This is a comparative and non-interventional study.

Study period: In the Medicine Unit-II of Nishat Hospital Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020.

Subjects and Methods: A total of 100 adult men (18-65 years) were selected, 50 of whom were smokers and 50 were non-smokers. ESR was performed with the modified Westergren method, and the lipid profile was performed with a chemical analyzer (Microlab 300 MERCK).

Results: A significant increase in ESR, total cholesterol (TC), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-c) and mean serum triglyceride (TG) levels was observed in smokers compared to non-smokers. Whereas, serum levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL-c) cholesterol were significantly lower in smokers compared to nonsmokers.

Conclusion: Smoking has an adverse effect on the lipid profile and ESR, thereby increasing the risk of atherosclerosis.

Key words: total serum cholesterol, ESR, smoking.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cigarette smoke damages the endothelium by generating free radicals such as nitric oxide and hydrogen peroxide. This oxidative stress promotes a systemic acute phase response, thereby increasing inflammatory cytokines, C-reactive protein, fibrinogen, blood count, whole blood viscosity and clump formation. Ultimately, this leads to an increase in the value of ESR. Smoking cigarettes is a strong risk factor for atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. There is a direct link between the number of cigarettes smoked and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Many authors described an increase in serum TC, LDL-c, TG and a decrease in antiatherosclerosis cholesterol (HDL-c). Nicotine stimulates catecholamines, causing lipolysis and an increased concentration of free fatty acids (FFA) in the plasma, which further results in increased secretion of hepatic FFA and triglycerides along with very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-c) in the blood. The decrease in estrogen caused by smoking leads to a decrease in HDL-c, while hyperinsulinemia in smokers leads to an increase in cholesterol, LDL-c, VLDL-c, and TG due to decreased lipoprotein lipase activity.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Table 1: Lipid profile in non-smokers and smokers

Lipid Profile values/mg/dl	Non-smokers (n=50)	Smokers (n=50)	P value
Mean TC	175.0±19.0	193.0±24.0	< 0.05
Mean TG	152.0±30.0	196.0±64.0	< 0.001
Mean LDL-c	96.0±17.0	116.0±20.0	< 0.05
Mean HDL-c	45.0±5.0	42.0±6.0	< 0.001

Table 2: Erythrocyte sedimentation

Mean ESR value mm/First hour	Non-smokers (N=50)	Smokers (N=50)	P value
	4.0±1.0	9.0±2.0	< 0.001

DISCUSSION:

Mean serum total cholesterol level in non-smokers was 175.0 ± 19.0 mg / dl, while in smokers it was significant (P <0.05), i.e. 193.0 ± 24.0 mg / dl. These observations are similar to those of Muscat and Harris.¹⁰ The mean serum triglyceride concentration in non-smokers and smokers was 152.0 ± 30.0 mg / dl and 196.0 ± 64.0 mg / dl, respectively (p <0.001). These findings are consistent with Rustogi and Shrivastva. Mean LDL-c levels in nonsmokers and smokers were 96.0 ± 17.0 mg / dL and 116.0 ± 20.0 mg / dL, respectively (P <0.05), showing a significant increase in the number of smokers, similar to Rustogi et al. Mean HDL-c in non-smokers was 45.0 ± 5.0 mg / dl, and in smokers 42.0 ± 6.0 mg / dl (p <0.001). This finding is in line with the study by Rosenson, which found that HDLc levels decline in smokers. The values of the erythrocyte

This is a comparative and non-interventional study held in the Medicine Unit-II of Nishat Hospital Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. A total of 100 adult men (18-65) years of age were selected, of which 50, who had smoked at least five cigarettes a day for the past five years, were kept in Group I, while the remaining 50 weight-adjusted non-smokers were kept as non-smokers. control group II. Patients with renal failure, liver disease, endocrine disorders, diabetes, hypertension, alcoholism, obesity, and those taking lipid-lowering drugs or thiazide diuretics were excluded from the study. A detailed physical examination was performed in both groups. After an overnight fast of 12 hours, 3 cc of blood was collected, 2 cc of which was delivered to a tube containing 1.5 ± 0.25 mg / dl of (EDTA) to estimate the erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) by the modified Westergren's method and 1 cc was stored in a syringe for the lipid profile (TC, TG, LDL-c HDL-c) using a chemical analyzer called Microlab 3000 MERCK.

RESULTS:

Most smokers have smoked five or more cigarettes a day in the past five years. The results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

sedimentation rate given in Table 2 indicate a very significant increase in ESR (P <0.001) in smokers compared to non-smokers, which indicates a strong association of markers of systemic inflammation with smoking. These findings are consistent with Bennudez et al.

CONCLUSION:

A significant increase in ESR, total cholesterol, TG, and LDL-c was observed in smokers, while in the same group a reduction in HDL-c was observed, showing a higher risk of developing atherosclerosis in smokers compared to non-smokers.

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